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Challenges among Medical Students towards Blended Learning

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Abstract

The study investigates the challenges associated with blended learning, specifically in medical education. Blended learning poses several obstacles related to technology proficiency, internet connectivity, access to digital resources, educational methodology, and social isolation. Blended learning integrates traditional classroom instruction with ICT-supported learning. The study employed vital informant interviews and other qualitative methods to collect primary data from people working in the field. The study found that a lack of access to digital tools and technical literacy presents difficulties for students, especially those pursuing medical education. Furthermore, their inability to participate in blended learning is caused by insufficient internet access. The study also emphasized the necessity for students to acquire technical literacy and the significance of technology as a critical skill for the future. According to the report, educational institutions should help students become more digitally literate and have better access to digital resources. It also underlined the importance of having access to the Internet and the necessity of inclusive and accessible educational opportunities. The study's conclusions shed light on the difficulties with integrated learning and suggest overcoming them, especially in medical education. The study aims to provide practical solutions that actively include research participants to improve medical education students' blended learning experiences.

Keywords: *blended learning, social isolation, digital resources, internet connectivity, technological proficiency*

Introduction

This paper argues that blended learning has challenges that create gaps in building an engaging and successful learning environment. Blended learning is a cutting-edge idea that combines the benefits of traditional classroom instruction with ICT-supported learning, encompassing both offline and online learning. (Lalima, 2017). It became a well-liked strategy in higher education because of its adaptability and versatility to various learning scenarios. However, issues and difficulties that merit investigation, particularly in developing higher education institutions, obstruct effective and efficient teaching and learning delivery (Alvarez Jr, 2020).

One of the challenges is the utilization of technology. Castro (2019) stated that technology is marketed as a valuable tool for addressing educational disparity. It was supported by the theory of , which emphasizes that people adopt technology. It asserts that essential variables affecting technology uptake are perceived utility and simplicity of use. Understanding how students feel about technology when it comes to blended learning in medical education is essential. Integrating online and education, it adapts in real time depending on student responses to frequent formative assessments, making online learning more sophisticated and flexible (Kazakoff, 2018). It is affirmed by the Technological Acceptance Model, which incorporates several elements that affect technology adoption, such as social influence, effort expectation, performance expectancy, and enabling circumstances(George et al., 2014). Using UTAUT can help shed light on the difficulties in using mixed-learning technology in medical education. By improving the learning environment for both students and teachers by enabling them to engage in ways that would not have been practical in face-to-face or remote approaches, information and communication technologies (ICT) must be used effectively in course design (Serrano, Dea-Ayuela, Gonzalez-Burgos, Serrano-Gil, & Lalatsa, 2019).

One of the aspects is digital literacy. Digital literacy is the capacity for success in a digital context. It is an idea that has undergone significant alterations, has a technical skills focus, and incorporates aspects of personality related to cognition and attitude (Al-Sulaimani, 2023). Access to connectivity is vital in technology(Chervinska, Melnyk, & Galyuk, 2023). Mayr and Oppl (2023) state that “the equipment with hardware and internet connectivity is also a success factor of a blended-learning system.” The feature of accessibility of internet connectivity that satisfies the requirements of studying with the blended-learning system results from not ignoring internet connectivity.

Another challenge is the Educational pedagogy. Using blended learning technology in pedagogical practice improves the efficiency of the educational process in higher education institutions. It applies Moore's causal distance theory, which states a psychological and communicative gap between the teacher and the student in a new setting. It highlights how crucial it is to close this gap to improve learning outcomes Keegan (2005). It promotes partnership engagement between "teacher-student" partners, facilitates the development of digital skills, and enhances program learning results (Chervinska et al., 2023)—however, stated that depending on how much content and delivery methods may be altered by enabling technology, generally, to meet the unique needs of students.

One of the Strategies is the techno-pedagogy mapping. Techno-pedagogy mapping integrates pedagogical and technological elements to address the explicit relationship of how technology instruments can support and help pedagogical features (Bizami, Tasir, & Kew, 2023). Another is self-regulation; according (Union, 2020), the rapid progress of technology has altered how people learn and acquire new information, making online education advantageous. As a result, students must be more independent and engaged in their

education.

Social learning is also a challenge in blended learning, and one of those is self-isolation. Kintu, Zhu, and Kagambe (2017) stated that students may stop participating in online and blended learning if they cannot make friends, as this will cause them to feel alienated and lonely. It will affect the group dynamic. The degree to which members of a learning community feel involved and connected is known as social presence. Social Presence Theory is frequently applied to comprehend how technology affects social interactions in virtual settings (Moyo, Gerwel, Mutambara, & Singh, 2024). However, Pei, Poortman, Schildkamp, and Benes (2023) argue that students appreciate group learning but find it challenging to control group dynamics.

Adoption of blended learning requires institutional support (Graham & Halverson, 2023). According to Anthony Jnr (2022) states that institutional support for academic engagement is the most popular choice for lowering engagement barriers and boosting support for online and blended coursework participation. According to Hoste, cultural factors are distinguished, including masculinity against femininity, power distance, uncertainty avoidance, and individualism versus collectivism. It facilitates comprehension of how cultural norms affect conduct and communication (Hofstede, 1984).

However, to provide inclusive and accessible learning experiences that meet any hurdles to information acquisition, skill development, and experience, the entire spectrum of learner characteristics must be considered. These include physical, sensory, and perceptual talents, abilities, attitudes, and past knowledge (Draffan & Rainger, 2013).

Over the years, many researchers have developed theories and models to analyze the factors influencing use behavior or the intention to use, which are crucial substitutes for technology acceptance.

This study is guided by the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). This theory was developed by Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, and Davis (2003), which follows the concept of extending and incorporating a variety of technology acceptance theories. In the context of blended learning, UTAUT provides a valuable framework for understanding and addressing the key factors that influence student acceptance and effective utilization of blended learning technologies and approaches. The four main factors affect users' intent to use an information system and subsequent behavior are: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating condition.

Performance Expectancy: is the extent to which a person thinks they can improve their skills and eventually perform at their best on the job by using technology or a system for their practiced discipline, studies, or job. This element may play a role in determining how and why students embrace new learning approaches in the context of blended learning, utilizing the cutting-edge technology at their disposal to meet their learning goals.

Effort Expectancy: Technology acceptance is not just simply done by introducing technology or a system to its end-users. It also involves considering whether or not the system can be easily used or navigated. The ease of use and intuitiveness of the digital platforms and applications used in blended learning are crucial. If the systems are perceived as overly complex, it can hinder student adoption and engagement.

Social Influence: Institutional support, peer influence, and instructor modeling can shape student perceptions and acceptance of blended learning. The support and encouragement from instructors, peers, and the institutional environment can positively influence the students' acceptance and use of blended learning technologies.

Facilitating Conditions: Ensuring that the necessary infrastructure, resources, and support are in place to enable students to access and effectively use the required digital tools is essential for the success of blended learning.

Generally, the study will identify the challenges in the areas for development, respond to user concerns, and modify technology to meet changing needs in blended learning. For this investigation, only primary data were used. Key informant interviews were used to get primary data from people working in the field (KII). Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) are suitable for gathering ideas and data because they aim to conduct in-depth interviews with a chosen group of information-rich individuals who are likely to provide needed data, concepts, and understandings on the subject matter.

Research Questions

This study explores the negative issues of blended learning modalities in Davao Doctors Colleges Inc. Specifically, this study sought to accomplish the following objectives:

1. Describe the sociodemographic of the study participants in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. socioeconomic status;
 - 1.4. ethnicity cultural background; and
 - 1.5. geographical location?
2. Identify the challenges of students in blended learning;

Methodology

The purpose of this research is to investigate the challenges of blended learning in order to develop more practical and applicable solutions. The researcher intends to actively involve the study participants in this process, so that the solutions developed will be directly informed by their experiences and perspectives. The goal is to generate solutions that are more workable and aligned with the needs and experiences of the participants, by incorporating their answers, actions, ideas, feelings, and perceptions gathered through the research process. This approach aims to ensure the solutions are grounded in the real-world challenges faced by the individuals involved in blended learning.

The researcher employed a qualitative study design. When gathering data, qualitative approaches promote great depth and specificity and provide substantial information about a small number of individuals (Moser & Korstjens, 2018). The qualitative research approach in the social sciences has evolved to be well-suited for exploratory studies, allowing for the assessment of the complexity of a single phenomenon (Johansson, 2007). This study involves an in-depth analysis, contextual investigation, exploration, studying a single case, and detailed description and analysis of the challenges of blended learning among medical students following the research objectives. Therefore, the qualitative research method employed for the study is a case study. Howarth (2005) states that, case studies are a tool to analyze current real-world phenomena through an in-depth investigation of a small number of occurrences or interactions within their context. Case studies facilitate a deeper understanding of complex research issues (Harrison, Birks, Franklin, & Mills, 2017).

To exhaust and analyze the study-participants' answers, actions, ideas, sentiments, and perceptions, the researcher employed key informant interview (KII). Key informant interviews were used to obtain primary data from people working in the field (KII). Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) are a suitable method for gathering ideas and data because their main objective is to conduct in-depth interviews with a chosen group of information-rich individuals who are likely to provide needed data, concepts, and understandings on the subject matter (Crabtree, 1999). Creswell and Poth (2016) stated that the choice of key informants is quite important since these people should be experts on the research issue and be able to offer original, in-depth, and perceptive information. In order to promote candid and open conversations with key informants throughout the interviews, he also emphasizes how crucial it is to build a solid connection with them. In order to obtain the unique viewpoints and experiences of the subject matter experts, the researcher performed in-depth, one-on-one key informant interviews. This allowed the researcher and the informants establish a solid relationship and sense of trust.

Purposive sampling was used in this study since the participants were specifically chosen. Rather than being picked at random, the participants were specifically choose to be a part of the study based on predetermined criteria.

The participants were specifically chosen to fulfill the following criteria: they must be 22 years old, regardless of gender or marital status, be enrolled as medical students at Davao Doctors College Inc., and have at least one year of experience with blended learning. The purpose of this careful participant selecting process was to improve the quality and applicability of the study investigation.

The researcher sought to collect data from individuals who share these particular qualities in order to gain significant insights into the issues faced by this particular group of students when implementing blended learning. The researcher was able to guarantee that the participants could provide knowledgeable, pertinent viewpoints to address the study objectives by using the purposive sampling approach.

Additionally, this study did not use any secondary or pre-existing data—rather, it only used primary data sources. In order to guarantee that the data gathered would be specifically pertinent to the research objectives and context, it was decided to exclusively employ primary data.

Furthermore, data gathering started by identifying the respondents in accordance to the given criteria. Next, the data gathering instrument was developed. The data gathering instrument for the study is an interview-guide questionnaire which contains open-ended questions and probing questions that will produce in-depth, contextual information from the key informants and to explore emerging themes and allow flexibility during the interviews. After the interview guide questions were developed, the researcher then proceeded to arranging the schedule of the interviews by setting a convenient time to interview the key informants, either in-person or virtually. Then, the interviews were conducted following the interview guide. To make sure that the accurate data were collected, voice recording through mobile phone was used. Of course, prior to this, the key informant was properly oriented on the processes of the data gathering including and their consent was obtained to audio or video record the interview. Hence, the data gathering instruments used for the study is not only the interview guide but as well as the phone for audio and video recording.

After KII was finished, data analysis was done. This was accomplished by identifying important themes, patterns, and insights from the interview utilizing the transcriptions and notes. The data was then categorized and interpreted using theme analysis. Lastly, the views and contextual data from the informants to offer a deep, complex understanding of the research problem.

At last, a selected university research panel verified the themes and codes. This was accomplished by presenting the findings during an internal research presentation, to which the medical students, who are the study's primary stakeholders, were invited.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Sociodemographic Profile*

	Count	Percentage
Sex		
Female	51	45.45 %
Male	9	54.55%
Age (in years)		
18-21	58	96.7%
22- 25	1	1.7%
26-30	1	1.7%
Socio- Economic		
Upper Class or wealthy people	2	3.3%
Middle Class or professional and business people	47	78.3%
Low Class or poor people	11	18.3%
Ethnic Culture		
Bisaya	39	65.0%
Bol anon	1	1.7%
Bukidnon	1	1.7%
Cebuano	1	1.7%
Ilocano/	1	1.7%
Ilonggo	5	8.3%
Maguinda	4	6.7%
Mandaya	3	5.0%
Mansaka	1	1.7%
Maranao	1	1.7%
Tandagan	1	1.7%
Tausug	1	1.7%
Waray	1	1.7%
Geographic Location		
Rural	34	56.7%
Peri- Urban	16	26.7%
Urban	10	16.7%

Table 1. The sociodemographic characteristics of the research participants are described in detail in this section. The purpose of showcasing these profiles is to set the scene and enable readers to comprehend the subsequent stories, which are shown as challenges faced by the medical students in Davao City. It presented in terms of sex, age, socioeconomic status, and employment status; the majority of the students were aged 18-21 years old and female, with 51 participants (58 out of 60 participants). Regarding socioeconomic status, 47 out of 60 students are in the middle class, 2 students from the upper class, and 11 students are in the lower class status.

Table 2. *Lack of Technological Literacy and access to digital tools*

Narratives	Codes	Themes	Frequency
- The problem, sir, there are students who does not have a knowledge in technology and digital tools. Another problems in the poor signal of data or wifi , which commonly encountered by students. For this, it is difficult for for me to be part of blended courses.	Technology as a Crucial Skill for the Future:	Lack of Technological Literacy and Access to Digital Tools	4
- So, the difficulties that exist in blended learning are, first of all, the difficulty that students encounter during learning digital is that lack of knowledge with regards to the computer , not just for the computer, but for the tools that are used in blended learning. And the most challenging that can affect the students is that they might not be able to attend the class on time due to lack of knowledge or illiterate with regards to the tools or resources	Technological Literacy in Blended Learning:		
- For me, the difficulties that usually student experience is that lack of knowledge. I mean, I have a lot of time management, they tend to use their gadgets instead doing some activities in the class	Personal Perspectives on the Importance of Technology:		
- Regarding internet connectivity, sir, the only thing I've encountered so far is, poor internet connection that could disconnect our meeting			
- For the internet, sir, I love to seek and to connect strong signal			
- For me, working as a group in blended learning is really challenging because there are ideas that they might not grasp well due to unstable internet connections.			

In terms of ethnic-culture, most of the students are Bisaya with 39 participants, Illongo with 5 participants, Maguindanao with 4 participants, and Mandaya with 3 participants. The rest are 1 participant only. It implies that the students are 18-21 in major cities, and most females are in the middle class. Most of them are in the middle class and have Bisayan ethnic culture.

These sociodemographic profiles provide background information for the following stories, especially about the difficulties Davao City's medical students confront. They understand the experiences and difficulties covered in the following sections by being better aware of the participant demographics.

Table 2. The primary goal was identifying or categorizing the key themes that present difficulties for medical students pursuing integrated learning. Nonetheless, remarkable accounts of the research participants' strategies for overcoming their lack of technological literacy and access to digital tools.

This study identified access to digital resources and a need for more technology knowledge as two main obstacles to blended learning. Since most research participants are medical students in medical school, they are not well-versed in various forms of technology and lack technical literacy and access to digital tools. In order to better understand the experiences of the research participants, the two case studies that will be given will include further details on the component above. The biography of Arnett, a Biology student who aspired to become a nurse but a product of blended learning, is the basis for Narrative 1 and Rosalyn, a Radiologic Technology student, is the basis for Narrative 2.

Narrative Interview 1: Harry Potter

Harry Potter is a 20-year-old Biology student from a middle-class family who wants to become an influential doctor someday. He is diligent in his studies, willing to learn all the subjects, and very participative in his class. During the pandemic, he was very anxious about how he would deal with his studies until the school announced that it would be modular and blended learning and that the students would be required to provide a laptop or a cellphone. During that time, he always found difficulty because of the applications and tools that they were using. He said to himself:

“My problems in using learning digital skills po, I can't, like, sa paggamit sa computer, wala kayo kayo knowledge po about ana and then, I think that's the isyu sa akoo.”

Harry Potter's statement shows that more competence in digital tools and computer literacy will be needed. This affirms Davis (1989) study emphasizing that if technology is perceived as helpful in increasing productivity, effectiveness, or work performance, users are more inclined to embrace and employ it. Technology adaption is greatly influenced by the advantages that are seen to exist.

Due to the necessity of adopting educational instruction in technology, He found ways to learn digital tools and applications commonly used in the class.

“Sa paggamit ng technology sa classes po, parang na-improve yung skills po in terms of digital po.”

Because of his dedication, he gradually adapted to the flow of blended learning. Davis (1989) stated that Users' perceptions of the ease of use significantly impact their acceptance of technology. A user-friendly and intuitive interface contributes positively to effort expectancy.

Narrative Interview 3: Thinker Bell

Thinker Bell, a 19-year-old radtech student from a middle-class family, had a bad experience during the pandemic. At that time, she was always searching on YouTube for how she would use a particular application. According to her:

Well, technology, using technology in classes is like, parang na-gina-ready ta for the future po and then big ano din po siya sa skills namin into technology po. Kay, diba? Ang world karoon is more on technology na po and then now. We practice technology; we will have technological skills na po.

Despite his difficulty, she is always positive in blended learning.

Well, difficulties, there are many po. But I feel like ang most kayo ng, na yung mga apps or like technologies nga, hindi pa kayo ko aware kung saan siya paggamit, especially sa mga apps. And then, challenging siya for me. Okay. Kaya nang nabaguhan lang ko and then okay naman nun siya pa rin

This positivity is proven by Serrano et al. (2019), who argue that it has undergone considerable changes, focuses on technical skills, and adds psychological traits connected to cognition and attitude. Despite the crisis, she has mental fortitude and a sense of positivity.

The material presented talks about the difficulties students have while using blended learning, especially regarding internet connectivity and technology competence. It emphasizes how a lack of understanding of technology and digital tools negatively impacts students' capacity to engineer more actively in mixed-learning environments. It also highlights the challenges brought on by spotty internet access, which can cause disruptions to group projects and educational activities. According to Venkatesh et al. (2003), the TAM extension incorporates various aspects that drive technology adoption, such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and enabling circumstances. Therefore, UTAUT will help you understand the obstacles to implementing technology in medical education (George et al., 2014).

Offers individual viewpoints on the value of technology in the classroom and the difficulties posed by students' low levels of technical literacy. It emphasizes how important it is for students to grasp technology fundamentals to excel in mixed-learning settings and their

future employment. It was supported by(Serrano et al., 2019) that information and communication technologies (ICT) must be used successfully in course design to improve the learning environment for students and teachers by allowing them to participate in ways that would not have been possible in face-to-face or distant approaches.

Potential answers to the problems mentioned could be further explored in the discussion section. Some of these include giving students thorough training in technology, enhancing internet infrastructure, and putting alternate plans for group projects when dependable internet connections are unavailable. Talking about how these issues affect educational fairness and how institutions may help students from different technical backgrounds could also be beneficial, as Castro (2019) would agree that technology is positioned as a valuable tool for reducing educational disparities.

The results highlight the significant obstacles that internet access and technology literacy provide to blended learning and advocates for proactive steps to guarantee that every student can participate fully in digital learning.

Table 3. Challenges in Time Management for Remote Learning

Narratives	Codes	Themes	Frequency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I feel socially isolated in a blended learning setup. because, we cannot see personally my classmates. - feel very socially isolated. Because in a situation like this, you don't know any familiar faces because I am a transferred student. - If you have depression or anxiety, it adds stress because you feel like you are alone or isolated. - . Especially when you are isolated in one room for several years or months. And when this decreases, it becomes a struggle. It becomes a struggle - <i>, the only thing that I am socially isolated in blended learning is that the time management and aside from that, also lack of information</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty in Managing Time at Efficiency and Time Management Short Timeframes and Priority Setting 	<p>Challenges in Time Management for Remote Learning</p>	

Table 3. examines students' difficulties in setting priorities and managing their time, particularly in mixed and distant learning. The author discusses their ideas and personal experiences with time management and how it affects their academic achievement. Essential ideas from the text consist of the following:

Time management difficulties: Using technologically assisted instructional mapping is challenging, and time management could be more effective at home because of personal obligations and distractions.

Setting priorities and allocating time to finish tasks and projects are crucial, as the author emphasizes, mainly when dealing with constrained resources. According to Kazakoff (2018), it is critical to understand how students feel about technology when it comes to blended learning in medical education. it is critical to understand how students feel about technology when it comes to blended learning in medical education. It changes in real-time based on student responses to the challenges they face.

Difficulties with remote learning: Time management problems impeded medical students' experiences with blended and remote learning, making it challenging to balance personal and academic obligations.

Impact of personal responsibilities: Medical students' personal responsibilities and household duties made it even more challenging to manage their time effectively, affecting their ability to focus on their studies.

To sum up, the medical students' experiences with remote learning and time management emphasize how crucial good time management techniques are to success in both the personal and academic spheres. The difficulties they encountered serve as a reminder that individuals and students must have excellent time management skills to meet the demands of blended learning and remote learning.

These are supported by Keegan (2005) stating that course design, instructor-student contact, and the usage of technology determine the amount of transactional distance. Measures of perceived distance and its influence on learner engagement are examples of resonant data.

Narrative No 4: Marimar's Challenges and Triumphs

Marimar, a 19-year-old Radiologic Technology student, found herself navigating the problematic blended learning environment in the busy city of Davao amidst the academic hallways of learning institutions. She illuminates the route to success. Practice, learning from mistakes, and working with peers become the main concepts for improving digital abilities. Her experience talks about the challenges

of adapting and prosper in a digital environment. She recognized the difficulties of keeping discipline when studying at home while discussing time management. Distractions and difficulty sticking to timetables in a mixed-learning setting were significant issues.

It is tough to manage time if wala ka sa student po. So, Okay. There are times na na-ay mga distractions sa balay, then ma-ignone ni mo inuhang proper routine at ni mo hang mga schedule. So, when you are studying at home and applying blended learning, it is challenging po kay daghay mga distractions.

Her narrative focuses on the various problems that students run into while trying to manage their time when studying remotely. Her experience with blended learning serves as an example of how adaptability and resilience are essential for overcoming the challenges of distance learning. Marimar's fortitude in overcoming these obstacles has helped her academic career and given her a better knowledge of the challenges associated with distance learning.

Narrative No 5: Christian Dior and the Intricacies of Blended Learning

Christian Dior, a 20-year-old nursing student at Davao Doctors College, struggles with the complexities of blended learning in the busy city of Davao, where education and technology meet. Sitting across from the interviewer, he discusses the problems and opportunities posed by the convergence of traditional schooling and digital resources.

Moreover, the biggest challenge that can affect the students is that they might not be able to attend class on time due to a lack of knowledge or need to be literate regarding the tools or resources. That is it.

But he also enjoys playing video games, so he finds it difficult to prioritize.

I have a lot of time management; they tend to use their gadgets instead of doing some activities in class. Moreover, as for, I mean, as, I mean, for blended learning, I mean, time management is critical in regards to because you, as a student, should know how to manage your priorities and also your needs as a student and as a person.

Christian Dior considers his experience as the talk comes to an end, appreciating both its benefits and drawbacks. The conversation concludes with gratitude as Christian's observations are prepared to contribute to the growing corpus of research on remote education.

Table 4. *Challenge of Fostering Connection in Blended Learning Environments*

Narratives	Codes	Themes	Frequency
- I feel socially isolated in a blended learning setup. because, we cannot see personally my classmates.		Challenge of Fostering Connection in Blended Learning Environments	
- feel very socially isolated. Because in a situation like this, you don't know any familiar faces because I am a transferred student.	Social isolation		
- If you have depression or anxiety, it adds stress because you feel like you are alone or isolated.	Social Isolation and Its Effects		
- . Especially when you are isolated in one room for several years or months. And when this decreases, it becomes a struggle. It becomes a struggle	Impact on Mental Health and Communication		
- <i>, the only thing that I am socially isolated in blended learning is that the time management and aside from that, also lack of information</i>			
-			

Table 4 describes what it's like to be a student in a mixed-learning setting and emphasizes the negative effects of social isolation on communication and mental health. The following is a summary of the file's key ideas:

Social isolation: The absence of one-on-one interactions with peers in a blended learning environment might make students feel socially isolated. This might be especially difficult for transferred students because they need to familiarize themselves with the surroundings and its people.

Mental health: Social isolation may make depressive and anxious symptoms worse and make life more stressful for students. This is particularly true if they spend several years or months alone in a single room.

Difficulties with communication: The mixed learning environment may also make it difficult for students to connect and communicate effectively. This may exacerbate emotions of social alienation and detachment.

Time management: Keeping a balance between students' personal, academic, and social lives while adjusting to a blended learning environment can be difficult.

Lack of knowledge: Not knowing how to handle the online portion of the learning process is another problem with blended learning.

Students may find adjusting to new platforms and technology complex, exacerbating feelings of bewilderment and loneliness.

The discourse results and debate, taken together, demonstrate students' difficulties in a mixed learning setting, especially in communication, mental health, and social isolation. These difficulties significantly impact the general well-being and academic achievement of students. Educational institutions and instructors must take action against these problems by giving students the tools, resources, and support they need to interact and communicate successfully in the classroom.

Narrative No 6: Antonio Banderas, the Poised Interviewee

Antonio Banderas, the poised interviewee, a 21-year-old Nursing student provided an insight on the challenges on internet connectivity or internet access. He stated that the slow internet connection is a hindering factor especially in looking for resources for his course activities and assignments.

“For internet connectivity, sir, na akong na-encounter is, hinay din kayo, sir, ang, like, sa isa ka area na, like, leave-leave or, ano. Ang, ang ga-affect na niya, sir, na internet connectivity na hinay is, dugay ka siya, dugay ka ka-search, dugay ka ka, ano, sir, pangitag resources sa mga activities.”

Even with the challenges imposed by a slow internet connection, Antonio Banderas has no choice but to look for a place where there is a sufficient or strong internet connection so that he could catch up with his studies and school activities.

Conclusions

This study examined the critical challenges faced by medical students in Davao City, Philippines in adapting to the shift to blended learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The key findings highlight two major obstacles: 1) lack of technological literacy and access to digital tools, and 2) difficulties in time management for remote learning.

The sociodemographic profiles revealed that the majority of the participants were female, middle-class students aged 18-21 from Bisayan ethnic backgrounds. Many lacked foundational digital skills and struggled to utilize the various software and applications required for their online/hybrid courses. This digital divide exacerbated the challenges they faced in keeping up with course materials and participating effectively.

Additionally, the transition to remote and self-directed learning exposed difficulties in time management, as students had to juggle personal responsibilities, technical issues, and academic demands without the structure of in-person classes. Prioritizing tasks, minimizing distractions, and developing effective study habits emerged as critical skills needed to thrive in the new blended learning environment.

Overall, this study underscores the need for more robust technological support and training for medical students, as well as the importance of cultivating time management competencies to foster student success in integrated learning models. Addressing these key barriers can help ensure equitable access and optimize learning outcomes, particularly for vulnerable student populations.

Because of this, the researcher recommends to provide comprehensive technology and training support for teachers and students such as workshops and tutorials, implement time management strategies and study skills development, promote a culture of peer-to-peer support and collaboration and to apply Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) for strengthening institutional policies for blended learning to gauge performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions for all the stakeholders, to make sure that the objectives for implementing such a technology or system are obtained with less issues.

References

- Al-Sulaimani, R. Y. (2023). Accessibility of Blended Learning for Special Needs Students in Higher Education.
- Alvarez Jr, A. V. (2020). Learning from the Problems and Challenges in Blended Learning: Basis for Faculty Development and Program Enhancement. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 112-132.
- Anthony Jr, B. (2022). An exploratory study on academic staff perception towards blended learning in higher education. *Education and information technologies*, 27(3), 3107-3133.
- Bizami, N. A., Tasir, Z., & Kew, S. N. (2023). Innovative pedagogical principles and technological tools capabilities for immersive blended learning: a systematic literature review. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(2), 1373-1425.
- Castro, R. (2019). Blended learning in higher education: Trends and capabilities. *Education and Information Technologies*, 24(4), 2523-2546.
- Chervinska, I., Melnyk, N., & Galyuk, N. (2023). Blended Learning as an Innovative Organization of the Educational Process in Higher Education Institutions of Ukraine. *Journal of Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University*, 10(1), 216-224.
- Crabtree, B. F. (1999). *Doing qualitative research*: sage.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2016). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*: Sage publications.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS quarterly*, 319-

- 340.
- Draffan, E., & Rainger, P. (2013). A model for the identification of challenges to blended learning Approaches to Developing Accessible Learning Experiences (pp. 55-67): Routledge.
- George, P. P., Papachristou, N., Belisario, J. M., Wang, W., Wark, P. A., Cotic, Z., . . . Car, L. T. (2014). Online eLearning for undergraduates in health professions: a systematic review of the impact on knowledge, skills, attitudes and satisfaction. *Journal of global health*, 4(1).
- Graham, C. R., & Halverson, L. R. (2023). *Blended Learning Research and Practice Handbook of Open, Distance and Digital Education* (pp. 1159-1178): Springer.
- Harrison, H., Birks, M., Franklin, R., & Mills, J. (2017). Case study research: Foundations and methodological orientations. Paper presented at the Forum qualitative Sozialforschung/Forum: qualitative social research.
- Howarth, D. (2005). Applying discourse theory: the method of articulation Discourse theory in European politics: Identity, policy and governance (pp. 316-349): Springer.
- Johansson, R. (2007). On case study methodology. *Open house international*, 32(3), 48-54.
- Kazakoff, E., Macaruso, P., & Hook, P. . (2018). Efficacy of a Blended Learning Approach to Elementary School Reading Instruction for Students Who are English Learners.
- Keegan, D. (2005). *Theoretical principles of distance education*: Routledge.
- Kintu, M. J., Zhu, C., & Kagambe, E. (2017). Blended learning effectiveness: the relationship between student characteristics, design features and outcomes. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 14(1), 1-20.
- Lalima, K. L. D. (2017). Blended Learning: An Innovative Approach. (*Universal Journal of Educational Research* 5(1): 129-136, 2017)
- Mayr, A., & Oppl, S. (2023). Higher education at the margins—success criteria for blended learning systems for marginalized communities. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(3), 2579-2617.
- Moser, A., & Korstjens, I. (2018). Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 3: Sampling, data collection and analysis. *European journal of general practice*, 24(1), 9-18.
- Moyo, T., Gerwel, C. P., Mutambara, E., & Singh, U. G. (2024). Effect of Social Media Usage in Zimbabwe's Telecommunications Industry and Its Impact on Corporate Reputation Management Digital Public Relations and Marketing Communication Trends in Africa (pp. 47-67): Routledge.
- Pei, L., Poortman, C., Schildkamp, K., & Benes, N. (2023). Teachers' and students' perceptions of a sense of community in blended education. *Education and information technologies*, 1-39.
- Serrano, D. R., Dea-Ayuela, M. A., Gonzalez-Burgos, E., Serrano-Gil, A., & Lalatsa, A. (2019). Technology-enhanced learning in higher education: How to enhance student engagement through blended learning. *European Journal of Education*, 54(2), 273-286.
- Union, A. (2020). *The Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa (2020-30)*.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS quarterly*, 425-478.

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